

Gallium-containing mesoporous nanoparticles influence in-vitro osteogenic and osteoclastic activity

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ABSTRACT

Mesoporous silica nanoparticles were synthesized using a microemulsion-assisted sol-gel method, and calcium, gallium or a combination of both, were used as dopants. The influence of these metallic ions on the physicochemical properties of the nanoparticles was investigated by scanning and transmission electron microscopy, as well as N₂ adsorption-desorption methods. The presence of calcium had a significant impact on the morphology and textural features of the nanoparticles. The addition of calcium increased the average diameter of the nanoparticles from 80 nm to 150 nm, while decreasing their specific surface area from 972 m²/g to 344 m²/g. The nanoparticles of all compositions were spheroidal, with a disordered mesoporous structure. An ion release study in cell culture medium demonstrated that gallium was released from the nanoparticles in a sustained manner. In direct contact with concentrations of up to 100 µg/mL of the nanoparticles, gallium-containing nanoparticles did not exhibit cytotoxicity towards pre-osteoblast MC3T3-E1 cells. Moreover, in vitro cell culture tests revealed that the addition of gallium to the nanoparticles enhanced osteogenic activity. Simultaneously, the nanoparticles disrupted the osteoclast differentiation of RAW 264.7 macrophage cells. These findings suggest that gallium-containing nanoparticles possess favorable physicochemical properties and biological characteristics, making them promising candidates for applications in bone tissue regeneration, particularly for unphysiological or pathological conditions such as osteoporosis.

1. Introduction

Bone tissue is a dynamic organ that undergoes continuous regeneration [1]. The process of mineral deposition is carried out by osteoblast cells, which are derived from mesenchymal stem cells [2]. Conversely, bone resorption is accomplished by osteoclast cells, which are derived from monocytes [3]. The balance of these processes is crucial for proper bone regeneration, and an imbalance can lead to conditions such as osteoporosis [4]. Biomaterials can be developed to modulate their interaction with cells and regulate their differentiation into osteoblasts or osteoclasts [5–7].

In recent years, nanomedicine has emerged as a cutting-edge

discipline in the biomedical field [8–12]. Among various types of biomaterials, mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs) have garnered significant attention [8,13–15]. MSNs have been utilized as drug delivery carriers and for theranostic applications [8].

The textural properties of mesoporous silica nanoparticles such as high specific surface area and pore volume, along with their ability to be synthesized in various shapes and with different pore structures, have made them highly attractive for biomedical applications [8,15]. The versatility of synthesis methods also allows for the incorporation of therapeutic metallic ions into MSNs, expanding their potential as drug-free biomaterials that can be tailored to individual patient needs [16,17]. Biologically active metallic ions, including Ag, B, Ca, Ce, Cu,

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Ga, and Sr, offer diverse biological functions: they were reported to promote angiogenesis, osteogenesis, and antibacterial properties [17,18]. Additionally, the surface of MSNs can be modified with functional groups through the presence of silanol groups, further enhancing their versatility [19]. As a result, MSNs have emerged as powerful platforms for the development of multifunctional systems that can address various challenges in nanomedicine, tissue engineering, cancer treatment, and antibacterial applications [17].

Nanoparticles-based biomaterials have the advantage of interacting with tissues at a cellular level. Moreover, the bioactive glass nanoparticles (BGNPs) can affect the cell differentiation to osteoblast and osteoclast phenotypes that exhibit fundamental control over all stages of bone formation, it is thus important to control their activity through bone substitute materials such as BGNPs. It has previously been observed that bioactive glasses can stimulate osteogenesis cell cycling and enhance osteoblast differentiation, and as a result, shorten the time of bone tissue regeneration [20–22]. For example, Sun et al. [23] studied magnesium doped mesoporous bioactive glass nanoparticles (MBGNPs) (chemical composition 80SiO₂-10CaO-10MgO (mol %), and particle size between 100 and 200 nm) incorporated in gelatin scaffolds. The study showed that the incorporation of Mg-doped MBGNPs accelerated bone healing and shortened bone formation time in an in-vivo rat model [23]. In recent years, there has been an increasing interest in developing multifunctional BGNPs through doping with multiple therapeutic metal ions [17]. As an example of that, Naruphontjirakul et al. [24] developed Sr, Zn, and Ag-containing BGNPs (particle size 150 ± 30 nm). These nanoparticles enhanced cellular mineralization and ALP activity of human fetal osteoblast cell line (hFOB) in addition to their anti-bacterial properties and potential anti-cancer properties [24]. However, it is not always clear whether osteogenesis is caused by the chemical composition of BGNPs or other factors that play a role in osteogenesis. Ha et al. [25] showed that mesoporous silica nanoparticles can stimulate autophagy: this process increases osteoblast differentiation and mineralization [25]. However, the stimulation of autophagy is not related to the material chemistry, but rather to its size and shape [25]. The response of osteoblasts to BGNPs is thus not fully understood.

Despite the importance of osteoclasts, there is a lack of substantial evidence about their interactions with biomaterials. Only a limited number of studies is available in the literature. For example, Detsch et al. [26] studied comprehensively the effect of nanoscale 45S5 bioactive glass (particle diameter 20–60 nm) on osteoclastic differentiation of RAW 264.7 macrophage cells. The study showed that nanoscale bioactive glass particles enhanced the macrophage cell viability, proliferation, and differentiation to osteoclasts. On the other hand, Gómez-Cerezo et al. [6] studied the effect of mesoporous bioactive glasses (chemical composition 75SiO₂-20CaO-5P₂O₅ (mol %), and particle size between 10 and 40 µm) on osteoclastic differentiation of RAW 264.7 macrophage cells. The study showed that the presence of mesoporous bioactive glasses (concentration up to 1 mg/mL) did not affect RAW 264.7 cells differentiation to osteoclasts [6]. Yang et al. [27] studied the effect of sol-gel derived BGNPs (chemical composition 60SiO₂-36CaO-4P₂O₅ (mol %), and particle size ≈ 500 nm) and extracellular vesicles (EV) derived from bone marrow mesenchymal stem cells (BMSCs) on osteoclastic differentiation of RAW 264.7 macrophage cells. The study showed that BGNPs increased EV secretion from BMSCs. The combination of BGNPs and EV inhibited the differentiation of RAW 264.7 cells to osteoclasts [27].

Gallium is an important therapeutic ion due to its multifunctional biological effects, such as anti-cancer, anti-bacterial, and osteogenesis properties [28]. While gallium itself does not have a known role in biological systems, Ga³⁺ shares similarities with Fe³⁺ ions, such as their ionic radius, ionization potential, and electron affinity [28,29]. Because of these similarities, gallium has the potential to interact with iron-binding proteins, exhibiting an iron-blocking mechanism [29,30]. This mechanism renders gallium-based compounds potent against drug resistance [30]. Moreover, gallium is utilized in various types of

biomaterials as a dopant [28]. The osteogenesis effect of gallium is mainly associated with an inhibition of osteoclast activity and an increase in apoptosis-dependent cell death [28]. Gallium containing MBGs have been studied previously [31–36]. Gómez-Cerezo et al. [35] conducted a study on gallium-containing mesoporous bioactive glasses within the SiO₂-CaO-P₂O₅-Ga₂O₃ system, utilizing particles in a micron-sized range, and evaluated the effects of these glasses on both pre-osteoblast and osteoclast cells. The behavior of osteoblast and osteoclast differentiation was altered by the presence of gallium containing MBGs. In our previous study, we reported the synthesis of novel gallium containing MBGNPs which did not show any cytotoxic behavior towards MG-63 osteoblast-like cells [36]. Based on the reported results, gallium-containing BGNPs could be ideal candidates for tuning the differentiation of osteoblasts and osteoclasts for regenerative purposes in diseases like osteoporosis.

In this study, we synthesized mesoporous silica nanoparticles containing calcium and/or gallium. The influence of the addition of metallic ions on the physicochemical properties of nanoparticles was studied. The nanoparticles were extensively characterized using SEM, TEM, N₂ adsorption-desorption methods, XRD, and ICP-OES. The biological response of the nanoparticles towards osteoblast- and osteoclast-like cells was studied and discussed in relation to related previous studies in the literature.

2. Experimental procedure

2.1. Synthesis of nanoparticles

Nanoparticles were synthesized using the microemulsion-assisted sol-gel method, as described in our previous publications [36,37]. A schematic illustration of nanoparticle synthesis is given in Fig. 1. Briefly, 2.8 g of CTAB was dissolved in 150 mL deionized (DI) water under continuous stirring for 30 min at 30 °C. Then, 40 mL of ethyl acetate (EA) and 3.66 mL of ammonium hydroxide were added, and the solution was left stirring for 30 min. 14.4 mL of TEOS and appropriate amounts of calcium nitrate tetrahydrate and/or gallium nitrate hydrate were added stepwise in 30 minute intervals. The nominal composition of nanoparticles is given in Table 1. After stirring for 4 h, the precipitates were separated by centrifugation and washed 2 times with deionized water and 1 time with ethanol. The collected particles were dried at 60 °C overnight before the calcination step. Finally, the dried samples were calcined by heating the dried powder at 1 °C/min to 650 °C with a 3 h dwell time.

2.2. Physicochemical characterization

The microstructure of nanoparticles was examined using a scanning

Fig. 1. Schematic illustration of the synthesis procedure of nanoparticles (Created with Biorender.com).

Table 1
Nominal composition of nanoparticles (mol%).

Sample	SiO ₂	CaO	Ga ₂ O ₃
NPs	100.0	–	–
NPs-Ga	99.0	–	1.0
NPs-Ca	70.0	30.0	–
NPs-Ca-Ga	70.0	29.0	1.0

electron microscope (SEM, Auriga, Zeiss, Germany) and a (scanning) transmission electron microscope ((S)TEM, FEI Talos F200S, Netherlands). The average particle diameter was determined by ImageJ software (National Institutes of Health, Bethesda, MD, USA) using SEM images: at least 100 particles were measured for each sample. Powder X-ray diffraction experiments were carried out using an X-ray diffractometer (XRD, Panalytical Empyrean DY1098, UK) using CuK_α radiation. XRD patterns were recorded in a low-angle 2θ range of 0.6–8°, a step size of 0.01°, and in a 2θ range of 10–80° at a step size of 0.02°. FTIR spectra were obtained using FTIR spectrometer (Spectrum 3, PerkinElmer, USA) with 45 spectral scans in the range of 250–1500 cm⁻¹ at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ in an absorbance mode. The textural properties of nanoparticles were determined with the nitrogen adsorption-desorption method using a Micromeritics ASAP 2460 adsorption analyzer. The surface area was obtained by the Brunauer-Emmet-Teller (BET) method. The pore size was determined by the Barrett-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) method. The chemical composition of nanoparticles was determined quantitatively by the acid digestion method using an inductively coupled plasma–optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES, Varian MPX, USA). The samples were dissolved in an acid solution (6 mL HCl, 2 mL HNO₃, 0.5 mL HF, 5 mL H₃BO₃) using a microwave digestion system (Speedwave® four Microwave Digestion Systems, Berghof Products + Instruments GmbH, Germany).

2.3. Ion release behavior

The ion release test was performed in three different solutions: Tris/HCl buffer (50 mM, pH 7.4), sodium acetate/acetate acid buffer (100 mM, pH 4.5), and complete cell culture medium (DMEM containing 10 % Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS) and 1 % Penicillin-Streptomycin (PS)). A total of 75 mg of nanoparticles was immersed in 50 mL of each solution at 37 °C with an agitation of 120 rpm for up to 7 days. After the immersion period, all samples were centrifuged and filtered to remove the nanoparticles. The filtrates were then analyzed using ICP-OES (Varian MPX, USA). To establish the working curve, a series of three calibration solutions was prepared by diluting certified reference materials for Si, Ca, and Ga (Analytica, Prague, Czech Republic), which were used as stock calibration solutions. The internal standardization technique with scandium was employed to eliminate non-spectral interferences. The precision of the analysis for all ions was below 5 %. Each sample was analyzed in triplicate to ensure accuracy.

2.4. Cell culture

The pre-osteoblast bone/calvaria cell line (MC3T3-E1) and murine macrophage cell line (RAW 264.7) were utilized in this study. MC3T3-E1 cells were cultured in α-MEM (Gibco, Germany) supplemented with 10 % FBS (Corning, USA), 1 % L-Glutamine (Gibco, Germany), and 1 % PS (Gibco, Germany) at 37 °C in a humidified incubator with 5 % CO₂. The cells were harvested using trypsin-EDTA (0.25 %, Gibco, Germany) and resuspended in the cell culture medium. RAW 264.7 cells were cultured in DMEM medium (Gibco, Germany) supplemented with 10 % FBS and 1 % PS at 37 °C in a humidified incubator with 5 % CO₂. The cells were harvested using a cell scraper and resuspended in the cell culture medium. In this study, direct in-vitro cytotoxicity tests, cell staining, cell internalization and osteoblast differentiation studies were performed using mouse osteoblast-like cells (MC3T3-E1). Osteoclast

differentiation was carried out using mouse monocyte/macrophage-like cells (RAW 264.7).

2.5. In-vitro cytotoxicity

MC3T3-E1 cell viability after direct exposure to nanoparticles was evaluated using WST-8 assay (CKK-8 Kit, Sigma-Aldrich, Germany). Briefly, 10⁵ cells/mL were seeded in each well of 48-well plates and were allowed to grow for 24 h. Afterwards, the cells were directly exposed to NPs, NPs-Ga, NPs-Ca, and NPs-Ca-Ga at a concentration of 5, 10, 50 and 100 µg/mL. Cells cultured in the medium were used as positive control and cells in α-MEM with 6 vol% dimethyl sulfoxides (DMSO) were used as a negative control. Cell viability was measured after 48 h of direct contact with MBGNPs. After the treatment, the medium was removed from each well, and the cells were rinsed three times with phosphate buffered saline (PBS, Gibco, Germany). 400 µL of 1 % v/v WST-8 in a cell medium solution was added in each well and incubated for 3 h. WST-8 solution without cells was also incubated and used as a blank. Aliquots of 100 µL from each well were transferred to a new 96 well-plate for spectrometry measurements with a microplate reader (FLUOstar Omega, BMG Labtech, Germany) at 450 nm. The experiments were performed in triplicate. The cell viability was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Cell viability (\%)} = \frac{(\text{Absorbance of sample} - \text{Absorbance of blank})}{(\text{Absorbance of positive control} - \text{Absorbance of blank})} \times 100$$

To investigate cell viability further, the cells were stained with calcein acetoxymethyl-ester (Calcein-AM, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Germany) and propidium iodide (PI, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Germany) which selectively stain live or dead cells, respectively. Cells were washed with PBS to remove the remaining cell culture medium and nanoparticles. Afterwards, 4 µg/mL Calcein-AM and 5 µg/mL propidium iodide containing Hank's balanced salt solution (HBSS, Gibco, Germany) were added to the cells and incubated for 30 min in the dark. Then the cells were put in a fixing solution (4 % (w/v) paraformaldehyde in PBS) for 15 min. Fluorescence images were taken using a fluorescence microscope (Axio observer, Carl Zeiss).

2.6. Cell-uptake study of nanoparticles by holotomography microscopy

For holotomography imaging experiments, 5 × 10⁴ cells/mL were seeded into 32 mm µ-dishes (Ibidi, Gräffelfing, Germany). After 24 h, nanoparticles were added to a final concentration of 100 µg/mL and 200 µg/mL cell culture medium. Control samples were supplemented with the same amount of cell culture medium. After incubation of another 24 h, cells were washed with PBS, fixed with 4 % (w/v) paraformaldehyde in PBS for 15 min, and imaged by 3D holotomography microscopy (Nanolive Fluo-3D Cell Explorer®, NanoLive, Tolochenaz, Switzerland) [38]. Cells, cellular structures, and nanoparticle clusters were visualized by digital staining based on differences in refractive index intensity. In all samples, the settings of the digital staining were kept constant to ensure a reliable quantification of the stained volume. To achieve a strong significance, each sample was investigated in two experiments with a total of 36 to 54 images and 101 to 167 single cells. The refractive index volume of each image was normalized to the cell number and data sets were analyzed.

2.7. Fluorescence microscopy assay

To assess cell morphology after 48 h of exposure to the nanoparticles, MC3T3-E1 cells were seeded in 24-well plates at a density of 10⁵ cells/mL. The cells were incubated with various concentrations of nanoparticles (5, 10, 50, 100, and 500 µg/mL). Additionally, positive control (cells cultured in α-MEM) and negative control group (cells cultured in α-MEM containing 6 vol% DMSO) were also used for fluorescence

microscopy observations. After 48 h of incubation, the cells were washed three times with PBS to remove any remaining nanoparticles. Subsequently, the cells were fixed in 4 % (w/v) paraformaldehyde in PBS for 15 min and permeabilized using a permeabilization buffer containing Triton-X 100 for 5 min. To visualize the F-actin cytoskeleton, the cells were stained with rhodamine phalloidin (R415, Molecular Probes, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Germany). Additionally, the cell nuclei were stained with a blue-fluorescent dye, DAPI (4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole, dihydrochloride, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Germany). Following staining, the cells were washed three times with PBS, and a fluorescence microscope (Axio Observer, Carl Zeiss) was used to capture the images.

2.8. In-vitro osteogenic studies

The effect of nanoparticles on the behavior of pre-osteoblast MC3T3-E1 cells towards osteoblasts was studied. For the differentiation study, an osteogenic differentiation medium was prepared. Initially, a complete cell culture medium (CCM) was prepared using α -MEM supplemented with 10 % FBS and 1 % PS. Then, 50 μ g/mL L-ascorbic acid, 10 mM β -glycerophosphate, and 10 nM dexamethasone were added to the CCM to create an osteogenic differentiation medium (osMEM).

Cells were seeded at a density of 2.5×10^4 cells/mL in a 24-well plate and incubated for 24 h at 37 °C with 5 % CO₂ to allow them to attach to the plate. Subsequently, the cell medium was replaced with osMEM containing nanoparticles at the concentrations of 10, 50, and 100 μ g/mL, and the cells were cultured for up to 14 days. The medium was changed every 2 to 3 days during the culture period.

To evaluate the influence of gallium on osteoblast differentiation, the specific alkaline phosphatase (ALP) activity was measured after 7 and 14 days in the presence of nanoparticles at the concentrations of 10, 50, and 100 μ g/mL. ALP expression was measured using an assay based on the enzymatic cleavage of nitrophenylphosphatases (pNpp) by ALP, resulting in the production of p-nitrophenol (pNp). Cell lysates were prepared by centrifuging the samples, and 250 μ L of the supernatant was mixed with 100 μ L of a 2.36 mg/mL pNp solution. The mixture was incubated at 37 °C for 30 min, and the reaction was stopped by adding 650 μ L of 1 M NaOH solution. The absorbance was measured at 405 nm using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The total protein content of the samples was determined using the Bradford protein test. For this, 25 μ L of cell lysates were mixed with 975 μ L of the Bradford protein assay kit, and after 10 min incubation in the dark, the absorbance was measured at 595 nm. The specific ALP activity was calculated based on the ALP measurement and the Bradford test and presented as the activity of hydrolyzing a certain amount of nanomolar para-nitrophenylphosphatase (pNPP) per minute and milligram of total protein. Additionally, the OsteoImage™ Mineralization Assay kit (Lonza, USA) was used to investigate the development of the mineral phase by osteoblasts. Stained cells were examined using a fluorescence microscope (Axio Observer, Carl Zeiss, Germany).

2.9. In-vitro osteoclast differentiation studies

The effect of nanoparticles on the expression of TRAP and actin ring formation, which are part of osteoclastic differentiation of RAW 264.7 cells, was investigated. 1.5×10^4 cells/mL were seeded in 24 well-plate and incubated for 24 h (37 °C and 5 % CO₂), to allow cell attachment on the well-plate. The cells were cultured with DMEM containing 10 % FBS and 1 % PS. Additionally, differentiation medium (osDMEM) was supplemented with macrophage colony-stimulating factor (mouse M-CSF, 25 ng/mL, Miltenyi Biotec GmbH, Germany) and the receptor activator of the NF- κ B ligand (mouse RANKL, 40 ng/mL, Miltenyi Biotec GmbH, Germany). The cells were then cultured with osDMEM containing nanoparticles (10, 50 and 100 μ g/mL) for up to 14 days. After 7 and 14 days, the cells were stained with tartrate-resistant acid phosphatase according to the manufacturer's instructions (TRAP staining kit, 387A, Sigma-Aldrich, USA). To further quantify the TRAP staining, DMSO was

added, and the plate was centrifuged for 20 min at 150 rpm at room temperature in the dark, and the optical density was measured at 562 nm [39]. To visualize the actin ring formation, the cells were stained with rhodamine phalloidin and DAPI. Finally, the cells were examined using a fluorescence microscope (Axio Observer, Carl Zeiss, Germany).

3. Results

3.1. Physicochemical characterization of nanoparticles

Fig. 2 shows SEM images and particle size distributions of the nanoparticles. SEM images show that spherical and elongated shaped nanoparticles without agglomerations were obtained by microemulsion-assisted sol-gel method. The analysis of the particle size distribution showed that the average diameter of nanoparticles was affected by their chemical composition (Fig. 2 and Table 2). The average particle diameter increased as a result of the addition of calcium and/or gallium. The addition of calcium showed the most profound influence (particle size increase from 70 ± 19 nm to 135 ± 49 nm). The addition of metallic ions also influenced the shape of the nanoparticles. Table 2 provides a summary of the aspect ratio of nanoparticles, where an aspect ratio of 1 indicates a spherical particle shape. The aspect ratio of NPs is the closest to a spherical shape, whereas the introduction of additional metallic ions to the system leads to elongated particles. The chemical composition of nanoparticles was analyzed by ICP-OES after an acid digestion. The chemical composition of NPs-Ca, NPs-Ga, and NPs-Ca-Ga was determined to be (90.9 ± 0.5) SiO₂ - (9.1 ± 0.5) CaO, (98.2 ± 0.1) SiO₂ - (1.8 ± 0.1) Ga₂O₃, and (88.8 ± 1.8) SiO₂ - (8.4 ± 1.2) CaO - (2.8 ± 0.6) Ga₂O₃ (wt%), respectively. As expected, the amount of incorporated calcium was lower than the nominal composition for both calcium-containing samples. The NPs-Ca-Ga analysis confirmed a significantly higher content of gallium compared to the NPs-Ga composition.

Fig. 3-A shows the results of the XRD analysis, which indicate that all nanoparticles compositions are X-ray amorphous. The chemical structure of the nanoparticles was investigated by FTIR spectroscopy (Fig. 3-B). The FTIR spectra of all compositions exhibited characteristic features of gel-derived silicate glasses [40–42]. The presence of a broad weak band between 3000 and 3600 cm⁻¹ corresponds to the O-H stretching vibrations [42]. A broad band in the range of 1250–1000 cm⁻¹ corresponds to transverse optical (TO) modes of Si-O-Si stretching vibrations [40]. The relative intensity of Si-O-Si stretching vibrations increased with the concentration of SiO₂, which could explain the decrease in the intensity of bands observed in the calcium and/or gallium containing samples [40]. Another band at around 800 cm⁻¹ was attributed to Si-O wagging vibration [40]. Additionally, a band near 460 cm⁻¹ was attributed to the O-Si-O bending vibration [41].

The mesoporous nature of nanoparticles is demonstrated in Fig. 4 by their TEM images. The results of the TEM analysis were consistent with the results of the SEM observations. NPs-Ca composition shows the highest particle size. All nanoparticle compositions showed disordered pore structure. Pore structures can also be categorized as radial-shaped, and this characteristic is more pronounced in NPs and NPs-Ga compositions. To better understand the mesoporous structure, the nanoparticles were characterized by N₂ adsorption-desorption and XRD analysis (Fig. 5). Ordered mesoporous structures can function as a lattice, displaying diffraction at low 2 theta angles [31]. The low-angle XRD measurements presented in Fig. 5-A show that all nanoparticle compositions exhibited a broad diffraction maximum at 2.5°. Notably, NPs and NPs-Ga compositions displayed the highest intensity, while the intensity of the diffraction maximum was significantly reduced for the NPs-Ca and NPs-Ca-Ga compositions. These findings, coupled with TEM observations, suggest that the radial-shaped pores possess some degree of structural order. However, the introduction of calcium or calcium-gallium disrupted the order in the pore structure, leading to a reduction in diffraction intensity. N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms (Fig. 5-B) could be identified as type IV isotherms characteristic of

Fig. 2. SEM images and particle size distribution of the nanoparticles investigated.

Table 2
Physicochemical characterization of nanoparticles.

Sample	SSA (m ² /g)	Pore Volume (cm ³ /g)	Particle Size (nm)	Particle aspect ratio
NPs	930	0.86	70 ± 19	1.07 ± 0.07
NPs-Ga	972	0.78	101 ± 27	1.18 ± 0.15
NPs-Ca	546	0.46	135 ± 49	1.18 ± 0.17
NPs-Ca-Ga	344	0.36	104 ± 33	1.20 ± 0.22

mesoporous materials [43]. Table 2 summarizes the obtained specific surface area and total pore volume data. Changes in the chemical composition (Table 1), especially the addition of calcium, have drastically affected the textural properties of nanoparticles. Specific surface area and total pore volume were reduced to half with the addition of

calcium.

3.2. Ion release behavior

Ion release behavior of nanoparticles was extensively studied using three different media as shown in Fig. 6. Tris (pH 7.4), and acetate (pH 4.5) buffers were used to understand the pH dependent ion release behavior of the nanoparticles. In Tris buffer, NPs-Ca and NPs-Ca-Ga compositions showed a burst release of silicon during the first 24 h of incubation. Then, the silicon concentration reached a maximum after 72 h of incubation. Their calcium-free counterpart showed a steady release of silicon ions up to 168 h of incubation in Tris buffer. Silicon release in acetate buffer was significantly lower compared to the one in Tris buffer. For all chemical compositions, silicon was released to the medium at a much slower rate during all incubation periods (up to 168 h). A similar calcium release profile for both calcium containing

Fig. 3. A) X-ray diffraction patterns, and B) FTIR spectra of nanoparticles.

Fig. 4. TEM images of the investigated nanoparticles.

Fig. 5. A) Low-angle X-ray diffraction patterns, B) Nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherm plots, and C) pore size distribution of the investigated nanoparticles.

compositions (NPs-Ca and NPs-Ca-Ga) was observed at both pH. NPs-Ca-Ga composition showed a slightly lower amount of calcium released compared to NPs-Ca, however, both compositions followed the same trend of the ion release profile. Gallium release did not show any pH dependent release behavior. For both compositions and at both pH conditions the detection of Ga was mainly possible after 168 h of incubation.

To understand ion release behavior in a cell culture environment better, a CCM (DMEM containing 10 % FBS, and 1 % PS) was also used for the ion release test. Cell culture medium showed an opposite behavior compared to the Tris buffer. Calcium-free samples showed a burst release of silicon ions into the cell culture medium during the first

24 h of incubation. However, the release of silicon ions from NPs-Ca, and NPs-Ca-Ga was slower in the cell culture medium. For all compositions the concentration of silicon was comparable after 168 h of incubation. Calcium concentrations showed similar ion release profiles in the cell culture medium, with a gradual increase in the calcium concentration in the CCM. It is important to note that CCM already contained calcium, so the increment of calcium concentration observed in the CCM when using the calcium-containing samples was lower compared to the increments observed in Tris and Acetate buffer. This result could be attributed to the mineralization/precipitation of insoluble calcium-phosphate crystals [44]. Gallium ions started to be released already after 4 h of incubation in the cell culture medium.

Fig. 6. Ion release profiles of nanoparticles in A) Tris buffer (pH 7.4), B) Acetate buffer (pH 4.5), and C) cell culture medium (DMEM containing %10FBS and %1PS).

3.3. In-vitro biocompatibility

MC3T3-E1 cell viability was measured after 48 h of direct exposure to nanoparticles at concentrations of 10, 50, 100, and 500 µg/mL, alongside positive and negative control groups (Fig. 7). The absorbance of positive control was measured with the cells cultured only in cell culture medium, and the average absorbance value of the positive control was normalized to 100 %. Up to the concentration of nanoparticles of 100 µg/mL all samples showed nonsignificant differences in cell viability compared to the positive control group. The cell viability only starts to significantly decrease at 500 µg/mL of NPs, NPs-Ga, and NPs-Ca. The strongest decrease in cell viability (34 %) was observed at 500 µg/mL of NPs-Ga. On the other hand, NPs-Ca-Ga did not show any significant drop in cell viability even at the concentration of 500 µg/mL. Furthermore, notable differences were observed among nanoparticle compositions at identical concentrations, particularly at the lowest (10 µg/mL) and highest (500 µg/mL) concentrations. At 10 µg/mL concentration, both calcium-containing samples displayed significantly lower cell viability compared to samples without calcium. Conversely, NPs-Ga

at a concentration of 500 µg/mL exhibited significantly lower cell viability compared to other samples at the same concentration.

Fig. 8 shows fluorescence microscopy images taken after the cell viability assay in direct contact with 10, 50, 100, 500 µg/mL concentrations of the NPs-Ga sample, along with positive (CNT +) and negative (CNT -) control groups. First, the cells were stained with Calcein-AM/PI (Fig. 8-A) before the fixation process. Calcein-AM (colored in green) stains live cells selectively, and PI (colored in red) stains selectively dead cells. The live/dead staining results showed results supporting the cell viability assay. An increase and a high presence of dead cells can be only seen from the images with 500 µg/mL concentration of the NPs-Ga sample which was the only concentration with a significantly negative effect on cell viability. The morphology of cells was visualized by staining with rhodamine phalloidin (for F-actin filaments in red), and DAPI (for nuclei in blue) as can be seen in Fig. 8-B. Adherent MC3T3-E1 cells displayed their phenotypical morphology after incubation in the presence of nanoparticles. The morphology and cell spreading behavior on well-plate was not affected by the addition of nanoparticles up to the concentration of 100 µg/mL. Fluorescence images of the cells incubated

Fig. 7. Relative cell viability of MC3T3-E1 cells cultured directly with nanoparticles for 48 h. Statistical significances are indicated with *. The respective confidence intervals are $p < 0.05$ and were calculated via one-way ANOVA with Bonferroni correction.

Fig. 8. Fluorescence microscopy images of MC3T3-E1 cells stained with A) Calcein AM/PI, and B) Rhodamine phalloidin/DAPI. Cells were cultured in direct contact with NPs-Ga, in concentrations 10, 50, 100, and 500 µg/mL, for 48 h. CNT (+) images show cells after 48 h in the absence of nanoparticles, and CNT (-) images show cells after 48 h, with 6 vol% DMSO containing cell culture medium.

with all samples at the concentration of 100 µg/mL are shown in Fig. 9.

3.4. Determination of cell associated nanoparticles by holotomographic microscopy

The cellular and cell membrane-associated nanoparticle load is known to be dependent on the particle concentration added to the cell culture medium [45,46]. To determine the particle content, non-invasive and label-free holotomographic imaging microscopy which is based on the specific refractive index (RI) of cells and cell components was used (Fig. 10) [38]. For imaging, MC3T3-E1 cell line with defined concentrations of NPs-Ca and NPs (100 µg/mL and 200 µg/mL) were incubated for 24 h and the cellular RI intensities were determined. As even untreated cells contain structures with high contrast and increased

RI, such as specific vesicles and condensed DNA, a reliable determination of cell-associated nanoparticles was only possible for cells that contained a sufficiently large number of particles. Consequently, differences in RI intensity between control samples and cells treated with NPs-Ca and NPs become significant only at higher concentrations (200 µg/mL) (Fig. 10-D). The lateral view of the 3D images shows some areas with high RI outside the cellular plane, strongly indicating the presence of extracellular particle agglomerates and a partial instability of the particles in the used cell culture medium (Fig. 10-C).

3.5. Effect of nanoparticles on osteoblastic activity of MC3T3-E1 cells

To evaluate the effect of nanoparticle addition on the behavior of pre-osteoblast cells, cell culture tests were carried out in the presence of

Fig. 9. Fluorescence microscopy images of MC3T3-E1 cells stained with Rhodamine phalloidin/DAPI. Cells were cultured in direct contact with nanoparticles, in a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, for 48 h.

nanoparticles at concentrations up to 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ in osteogenic cell culture medium for 7 and 14 days. After each time point, cell viability (Fig. 11-A) and ALP activity (Fig. 11-B) were analyzed. In addition, cellular mineralization was visualized using OsteoImage™ fluorescence staining (Fig. 11-D) and quantified using a fluorescence microplate reader (Fig. 11-C).

The results of the cell viability test indicated that the addition of nanoparticles led to a slower rate of cell proliferation after 7 days of incubation in osteogenic cell culture medium. This effect was especially pronounced in the gallium-containing samples. As the concentration of gallium-containing nanoparticles increased, cell viability decreased. The lowest cell viability was observed in the NPs-Ca-Ga samples at a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The addition of nanoparticles without gallium led also to a decrease in cell viability, but higher concentrations did not have any negative effect on cell viability. After 14 days of incubation, the cell viability slightly increased, with the exception of two samples namely, NPs-Ga (100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) and NPs-Ca-Ga (50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). The difference in cell viability for 7 and 14 days was more distinct with the addition of nanoparticles compared to the control group.

Overall, the addition of nanoparticles led to a higher production of ALP by MC3T3-E1 cells after 7 days of incubation than in the control group. However, higher concentrations of nanoparticles, especially those containing gallium, had a negative effect on ALP production. The ALP production was almost doubled after 14 days of incubation in the control group, but this increase was not observed in the cells incubated with nanoparticles. Instead, the ALP production levels remained similar or decreased after 14 days of incubation.

The nanoparticles were also found to enhance the ability of MC3T3-E1 cells to mineralize their extracellular matrix. The chemical composition of the nanoparticles had a significant effect on mineralization, with calcium-containing nanoparticles showing a prominent effect. The effect of calcium-containing nanoparticles on mineralization was more pronounced at higher concentrations. Specifically, the 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ concentration of calcium-containing nanoparticles resulted in a 4–5-fold increase in mineralization compared to the control group (Fig. 11-C).

3.6. Nanoparticles effect on osteoclast differentiation of RAW 264.7 cells

To evaluate the effect of nanoparticle addition on the differentiation of macrophages (RAW 264.7 cell line) into osteoclasts, cell culture tests were carried out in the presence of nanoparticles at concentrations of up to 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ in cell culture media supplemented with M-CSF and RANKL for 7 and 14 days. The control group without nanoparticles was included for comparison (Fig. 12-A). The results show that the addition of nanoparticles significantly increased the cell viability after 7 days of incubation, especially at higher concentrations of nanoparticles. The most prominent effect was observed with 50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of nanoparticles with the NPs-Ca-Ga composition. The cell viability results were similar to the control group after 14 days of incubation. Fig. 12-B shows the effect of nanoparticles on the TRAP positive cells which indicates osteoclasts, as measured by the optical density of the TRAP dosage of cellular extract at 562 nm. The TRAP staining images are shown in Fig. 12-C. The TRAP expression of osteoclasts was affected by the presence of nanoparticles. The addition of a high concentration of gallium-containing nanoparticles led to a decrease in TRAP positive cells, with the lowest numbers of TRAP positive cells observed in the group treated with 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of NPs-Ga after both 7 and 14 days of incubation. The combined findings of cell viability and TRAP positive cells results indicate that the TRAP activity did not increase over time with a higher number of cells in total, particularly with the addition of 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of NPs-Ga.

These results imply that gallium-containing nanoparticles influence the differentiation of RAW 264.7 cells into osteoclasts. Notably, there is a significant variation in cell viability during the differentiation studies in the presence of NPs, which makes it challenging to assess the impact of nanoparticles solely through the measurement of TRAP dosage of cellular extracts. The findings indicate that at higher concentrations of both gallium-containing samples, there is a significant reduction in the number of TRAP-positive cells. However, it is worth noting that only the cells treated with NPs-Ca-Ga exhibited cell viability results similar to those of the control group. This suggests that NPs-Ca-Ga may have a more favorable impact on inhibiting osteoclasts compared to the other gallium-containing samples, warranting further investigation into its potential therapeutic applications.

Fig. 10. Holotomographic imaging of cellular and cell associated nanoparticles. MC3T3-E1 cell line with unlabeled NPs-Ca and NPs are visualized by changes of the refractive index. A) Confocal 2D RI image. B) and C) Representative 3D RI images under different angles (top view and lateral view). Structures with low RI, such as cytoplasm and cell nuclei, were digitally stained in green, whereas structures with high RI, such as particle agglomerates, were digitally stained in red. D) Quantification of cellular and cell-associated areas with high RI intensity, such as nanoparticle clusters. Statistical significances are indicated with ***. The respective confidence intervals are $p < 0.0002$ and were calculated via *t*-test analysis. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

To further evaluate the osteoclast activity of macrophage cells, the formation of actin rings was examined. The actin ring is one of the key signs of mature osteoclasts [27]. Fig. 12-D shows fluorescence microscopy images of RAW 264.7 cells stained with rhodamine phalloidin/DAPI in the concentration of 100 µg/mL, after 14 days of incubation in the osteogenic medium. Mature osteoclasts formed an observable actin ring. The actin rings were not statistically different from the positive control group.

4. Discussion

This study aimed to assess the importance of gallium-containing mesoporous silicate nanoparticles in improving osteogenesis for bone tissue engineering applications. Previous studies have noted the significance of particle size on cell differentiation into osteoblast and osteoclast phenotypes. Ha et al. [25] demonstrated that silica nanoparticles

(particle size ≈ 50 nm) enhanced osteoblast differentiation and cellular mineralization. Conversely, Detsch et al. [26] showed that nanoscale bioactive glass nanoparticles (particle size between 20 and 60 nm) enhanced osteoclast differentiation. Therefore, mesoporous bioactive glass nanoparticles can enhance both osteoblast and osteoclast cell differentiation. It is also well known that gallium can inhibit osteoclast activity while enhancing osteoblast activity [28,35]. Gallium-containing mesoporous nanoparticle compositions thus have the potential to be excellent bone grafting materials for osteoporosis treatments. Accordingly, we prepared nanoparticles with different compositions to differentiate the effects of silica nanoparticles and bioactive glass nanoparticles (in the SiO₂-CaO system) with and without gallium addition.

The nanoparticles were synthesized using a microemulsion-assisted sol-gel method. This method minimizes the impact of additional metallic ions on the system [36,37,47,48], microemulsion droplets act

Fig. 11. Osteoblast differentiation study of MC3T3-E1 cells in the presence of nanoparticles. A) The cell viability of MC3T3-E1 cells at 7 and 14 days of incubation with 10, 50, 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ nanoparticle concentration. B) Specific ALP activity of MC3T3-E1 cells after 7 and 14 days of incubation. C) Effect on cellular mineralization of MC3T3-E1 cells after 7 and 14 days of incubation. Well-plates read on a plate reader using 492 nm excitation and 520 nm emission wavelengths. D) Fluorescence microscopy images after 14 days incubation with OsteoImage™ staining. Statistical significances are indicated with *. The respective confidence intervals are $p < 0.05$ and were calculated via *t*-test analysis.

as a barrier, preventing the nanoparticles from agglomerating [49]. As shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 4, SEM and TEM images show that the nanoparticles exhibited similar morphology with spherical shape and elongated pineal shape nanoparticles without agglomeration. The introduction of gallium did not have any impact on the size of the nanoparticles; however, calcium addition increased the particle size significantly as evidenced by the particle size distribution results (Fig. 2). These results are in line with previous studies [47,48]. There is a distinction between the nominal chemical compositions of the nanoparticles and their verified chemical compositions, as determined by ICP-OES. The measured compositions revealed a lower presence of calcium compared to what was originally designed. This behavior is commonly observed in bioactive glass nanoparticles synthesized by sol-gel methods [50,51]. The variation is generally attributed to the washing procedures conducted prior to nanoparticle drying [50]. During the centrifugation and washing steps following the synthesis of nanoparticles, some of the calcium precursor components may be removed from the system.

Due to its nature, microemulsion-assisted sol-gel method yields mesoporous nanoparticles with disordered pore structure [37,52]. The incorporation of metallic ions, such as calcium and gallium, disrupts the pore structure even further, as evidenced by low angle XRD measurements shown in Fig. 5-C. Mesoporous silica nanoparticles with ordered pore structure usually exhibit diffraction maxima at low angles (2θ), in the $2\text{--}10^\circ$ range [53]. In contrast, all nanoparticle compositions prepared in this work displayed only one broad and poorly resolved diffraction maximum, indicating a compromised and disordered pore structure [34]. The presence of calcium and gallium further reduced the intensity of the diffraction peak in the range $2\theta = 2\text{--}3^\circ$ in NPs-Ca and NPs-Ca-Ga, signifying an even greater disruption of the ordered pore structure. The results of nitrogen adsorption analysis showed that all nanoparticle compositions exhibited similar adsorption-desorption

curves (Fig. 5-A), with H4-type hysteresis loops [54]. The specific surface area of nanoparticles was reduced to about 50 % in both calcium-containing compositions (Table 2). This could be attributed to a change of ionic strength of the solution with the high concentration of calcium, that affects the interaction between TEOS and CTAB. These findings are in line with the results of low angle XRD analysis indicating an increasingly disordered pore structure. Previous studies report an average pore size of around 3 nm when using CTAB as a pore templating agent in mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs) [55], which agrees with the pore size measurements of the NPs prepared in this study. The addition of calcium and gallium led to a slight increase in pore size.

A strong relationship between therapeutic effects (e.g., osteogenesis, angiogenesis) and ionic dissolution products has been reported in the literature [18,21]. These biological effects are dependent on the concentration and type of ions. To understand the dissolution mechanism of nanoparticles, media with various pH and a complete cell culture medium were used (Fig. 6). The pH levels within cellular compartments vary. For instance, the intracellular pH typically ranges between 7.0 and 7.4. However, specific organelles, like lysosomes, maintain pH as low as 4.5, the nanoparticles can encounter such environment after internalization by cells [56,57]. Cancer cells are also characterized by an acidic extracellular pH and a higher intracellular pH compared to normal cells [56,57]. Consequently, comprehending how nanoparticles release ions in response to pH becomes important. The different pH conditions mainly affected the release of Si ions, with acidic pH conditions slowing down the release of Si ions. It is known that Si ions alone play an important role in proliferation, differentiation, and mineralization [58]. Ga ions were found to reduce the quantity of Ca and Si ions released into all three media. This effect is explained by the dual role of gallium ions in the glass structure, one of which is the formation of a more polymerized silicate network [59]. The decrease of the concentration of phosphorus ions in cell culture medium compared to the control group

Fig. 12. Osteoclast differentiation study of RAW 264.7 cells in the presence of nanoparticles. A) The cell viability of RAW 264.7 cells at 7 and 14 days of incubation with 10, 50, 100 µg/mL nanoparticle concentration. B) The effect of nanoparticles on the TRAP positive cells. The cells were cultured for 7 and 14 days with M-CSF and RANKL containing cell culture media, then TRAP dosage of the cellular extract was performed and optical density was read at 562 nm. C) Microscopic images of TRAP stained RAW 264.7 cells stimulated by M-CSF and RANKL for 14 days of incubation with 100 µg/mL nanoparticle concentration. D) Fluorescence microscopy images of RAW 264.7 cells stained with Rhodamine phalloidin/DAPI. Cells were cultured in direct contact with nanoparticles in the concentration 100 µg/mL for 14 days in osteogenic medium (Scale bar = 50 µm). Statistical significances are indicated with *. The respective confidence intervals are $p < 0.05$ and were calculated via *t*-test analysis.

indicates that both NPs-Ca and NPs-Ca-Ga compositions show bioactive behavior in the cell culture medium (data not shown here). These findings are in line with the bioactivity test results reported in our previous study [36].

Nanoparticles can induce cytotoxicity through various mechanisms

[60]. In a study conducted by Gómez-Cerezo et al. [35], the cytotoxicity of MBGs containing up to 7 mol% gallium was investigated using MC3T3-E1 pre-osteoblast cells. The results of the study indicated that the addition of gallium containing MBGs at a concentration of 1 mg/mL in the cell culture medium did not exhibit cytotoxic effects on pre-

osteoblast cells. Additionally, the researchers examined the impact of gallium containing MBGs on osteoblasts and osteoclasts differentiation. Their findings are aligned with the existing literature, demonstrating that gallium promotes early differentiation of osteoblast cells while inhibiting osteoclast differentiation [28,35]. In another study by Ciraldo et al. [61], gallium containing MBGs were coated onto a surface of 45S5 bioactive glass scaffolds constructed from natural marine sponges. The introduction of Ga-doped MBGs to the scaffolds increased their biocompatibility with MC3T3-E1 pre-osteoblastic cells. The addition of gallium also resulted in improved antibacterial properties of the scaffolds. In our previous research, we successfully incorporated gallium into mesoporous bioactive glass nanoparticles [36]. Based on the results of indirect cell culture testing, the gallium-containing MBGNPs exhibited no cytotoxic effects on MG-63 osteoblast-like cells. This finding highlights the cytocompatibility of gallium-containing MBGNPs in relation to osteoblast-like cells. In the present study, we assessed the viability of MC3T3-E1 cells by exposing them to nanoparticles at concentrations of up to 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ (Fig. 7). It is worth noting that the high concentration of nanoparticles can lead to re-agglomeration in culture medium, thereby affecting the exposure dose to the cells and potentially masking nano-cytotoxic effects [62]. Moreover, except for the NPs-Ca-Ga composition, all other nanoparticles displayed cytotoxic effects at the concentration of 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. This observation was further supported by the live/dead assay, which yielded similar results to the CCK-8 assay (Fig. 8). The cell density decreased significantly when exposed to nanoparticles at the concentration of 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. In the presence of nanoparticles, the rhodamine phalloidin and DAPI labeling demonstrated that MC3T3-E1 cells maintained their characteristic morphology and adhered to the surface of the well-plate.

Due to their small size, nanoparticles can interact with cells at the cellular level [63,64]. They can be internalized by cells and release ions or drugs intracellularly [63,65–67]. Therefore, nanoparticles can be more efficient compared to conventional biomaterials [65]. Nanoparticles can enter cells through several mechanisms, such as passive diffusion, endocytosis, and membrane penetration. Previous studies have shown that mesoporous silica nanoparticles are internalized by cells through receptor-mediated endocytosis mechanisms [66]. Cellular uptake is commonly measured using fluorescence microscopy, flow cytometry, or transmission electron microscopy [68]. In this study, we used holotomography microscopy, an advanced imaging technique that allows non-invasive and label-free visualization [38]. It provides detailed information about the refractive index distribution within the cell, enabling the visualization of cellular structures without the need for staining or labeling, which is an advantage over fluorescence microscopy or flow cytometry [38]. This study confirmed the nanoparticles internalization within the cells (Fig. 9). It is worth noting that the cellular uptake of nanoparticles can be influenced by various factors, including size, shape, surface charge, and surface functionalization of the nanoparticles, as well as the type of cells involved [69]. In this study, the used nanoparticles mainly differ in size, which plays an important role in the nanoparticle interaction with cells. The smallest nanoparticles were NPs, with an average size of 70 ± 19 nm, while the largest NPs-Ca had an average size of 135 ± 49 nm (Fig. 2). Therefore, both these samples were used for the cell uptake study. Similar refractive indices of the cells were observed for both nanoparticle compositions at concentration of 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. These findings indicate that nanoparticles of varying sizes interacted with the cells in a similar fashion. The literature also supports this finding. Slowing et al. [70] studied the uptake of MCM-41 type mesoporous silica nanoparticles with an average particle diameter of 150 nm by human cancer cells using fluorescence microscopy. They showed that silica nanoparticles in this size range can be taken up by HeLa cells. It was reported that the most efficient cellular uptake occurs at particle diameters of ~ 50 nm [69,71]. In the context of drug delivery applications, it is crucial for nanoparticles to be efficiently taken up by cells and to release their cargo within the cytoplasm. Understanding the mechanisms of internalization by cells is thus of utmost

importance. Additional investigations, such as quantifying the subcellular localization of nanoparticles, would provide valuable insights into the role of nanoparticles regarding cellular responses.

Nanoparticle concentrations of up to 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ were used for the differentiation studies due to a decrease in cell viability observed at a concentration of 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ (Fig. 7). In the present cell biology study involving pre-osteoblast cells, the presence of mesoporous nanoparticles with different compositions affected MC3T3-E1 cell proliferation, ALP activity, and mineralization capabilities in different ways (Fig. 11). Cell viability decreased with all types of nanoparticles. These results can be explained by the relationship between reduced cell proliferation and increased osteogenic differentiation. It is known that cells continue dividing before reaching a differentiated state, whereas fully differentiated cells cease the division cycle [72]. Cell proliferation was predominantly slowed down with NPs-Ca-Ga (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). The reduced cell proliferation rates also resulted in a decreased amount of alkaline phosphatase (ALP) activity. Additionally, the OsteoImage™ staining showed a much higher formation of hydroxyapatite (HA) with the addition of both calcium-containing nanoparticles. This contrasts with the ALP results, which can be explained by the fact that ALP is an early differentiation marker for the osteogenic cell lineage [3,73,74]. These results indicate that osteoblast differentiation started earlier than after 7 days, as confirmed by the observed higher in-vitro mineralization. Osteoblast cells stopped proliferating after differentiation [75], as supported by cell viability measurements.

Sun et al. [23] studied the osteoblast differentiation of MC3T3-E1 cells using the ionic dissolution of magnesium-containing MBGNPs after 7 and 10 days of incubation. Their findings on ALP activity in the MC3T3-E1 cell line were in line with the results of this study, showing a similar ALP activity for the control group and lower concentrations of nanoparticles. Nanoparticles are known to act as cell signaling cues through therapeutic ions such as silicon, calcium, and gallium to induce osteogenic differentiation, promoting bone regeneration [23,24,28,76]. To summarize, the addition of higher concentrations of NPs-Ca and NPs-Ca-Ga to the osMEM initiated an earlier osteoblast differentiation, leading to a decrease in cell proliferation. The reduction in cell proliferation was accompanied by a decrease in ALP activity, while cellular mineralization increased. Gómez-Cerezo et al. [35] also studied the effect of gallium-containing MBGs ($\text{SiO}_2\text{-CaO-P}_2\text{O}_5$) on MC3T3-E1 osteogenic differentiation. Although they did not perform any mineralization study, they showed that after 7 days gallium containing MBGs increased the ALP activity significantly compared to the control group and gallium-free MBGs. However, in the present study, both calcium containing mesoporous nanoparticle compositions affected the mineralization positively. The difference could be explained by the effect of nanoparticles. The nanoparticles themselves can stimulate osteoblast differentiation and mineralization [25]. Although the mechanism is still not completely understood, the study suggests that the addition of silica nanoparticles inhibits autophagosome formation which is blocked by the mineralization [25].

Gallium has been utilized in clinical settings for the treatment of cancer-related hypercalcemia [28]. Its mechanism involves reducing calcium release from bones by inhibiting bone resorption through the inhibition of osteoclast function [25,28,77]. Conversely, nanoscale bioactive glasses have been shown to enhance osteoclast differentiation [26]. Given the contrasting effects of gallium-containing and nanoscale bioactive glasses, it is important to understand the impact of gallium-containing nanoparticles on osteoclast differentiation. In this study, a concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of NPs-Ca reduced the viability of RAW 264.7 cells compared to the control group after 7 days, but it increased the differentiation of osteoclast cells. With the addition of 50 and 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of NPs-Ca and NPs-Ca-Ga, the number of osteoclast cells decreased with the NPs-Ca-Ga addition. The presence of NPs-Ca-Ga was found to suppress osteoclast differentiation, particularly when using higher nanoparticle concentrations and a lower level of released gallium (Fig. 12). These results align with those obtained by Gómez-Cerezo et al.

[35], who demonstrated that gallium-containing MBGs at a concentration of 10 mg/mL strongly inhibited osteoclast differentiation by approximately 60–70 % compared to the control group. However, it is important to note that this study employed lower concentrations of nanoparticles (up to 100 µg/mL), resulting in a minor effect of gallium. Furthermore, it presents a challenge to isolate the specific effects of individual therapeutic ions within the system. To gain a comprehensive understanding of the effects of gallium-containing mesoporous glass nanoparticles, further research is necessary, which may require the use of more advanced molecular biology approaches. This will allow for a more nuanced examination of the interactions and mechanisms at play within the system, contributing to a deeper understanding of the therapeutic potential of gallium-containing mesoporous nanoparticles.

To summarize, this study has shown that gallium can be successfully incorporated into mesoporous silica nanoparticles without significantly affecting their physicochemical properties. The results of the study also demonstrated the in vitro cytocompatibility of gallium-containing nanoparticles, their ability to promote mineralization and their influence on osteoclast-like cells. These findings suggest that these nanoparticles have potential applications in bone regeneration.

5. Conclusions

Mesoporous silica-based nanoparticles with the addition of calcium and gallium were successfully synthesized using the microemulsion-assisted sol-gel method. Well-dispersed nanoparticles exhibited a spherical and pineal shape with a diameter ranging from 100 to 200 nm. The incorporation of calcium ions had a significant impact on the textural properties of the nanoparticles, resulting in approximately 50 % reduction of the specific surface area. When added directly to the cell culture medium the nanoparticles did not exhibit any cytotoxic effects on MC3T3-E1 pre-osteoblast cells, even at concentrations of up to 100 µg/mL. Holotomographic microscopy study confirmed the uptake of both calcium containing and calcium-free nanoparticles by MC3T3-E1 cells. The presence of gallium and calcium in the nanoparticles enhanced their mineralization capabilities upon interaction with MC3T3-E1 pre-osteoblasts. The gallium-containing mesoporous bioactive glass nanoparticles affected osteoclastogenesis in RAW 264.7 cells. Considering their cytocompatibility and their effects on both osteoblasts and osteoclasts, these nanoparticles hold promise for bone regeneration applications, particularly in the treatment of conditions such as osteoporosis.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Fatih Kurtuldu: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Nurshen Mutlu:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation. **Ralf P. Friedrich:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Investigation. **Ana M. Beltrán:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Liliana Liverani:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Rainer Detsch:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Christoph Alexiou:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Dušan Galusek:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Aldo R. Boccaccini:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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